

COMPARATIVE EFFECTS OF CONCEPTS MAPPING AND SCAFFOLDING AS INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGIES ON STUDENTS' LEARNING OUTCOMES IN BASIC SCIENCE IN EKITI STATE, NIGERIA.

By

ILUGBUSI, A. A. and AKINWUMI, I. O.

*School of Sciences College of Education,
Ikere Ekiti, Ekiti State.*

Abstract

This study compared the effects of concept mapping and scaffolding as instructional strategies on students' learning outcomes in Basic science in Ekiti state junior secondary schools. The study sample consisted of 360 JSS 2 Basic science students selected from five junior secondary schools in Ekiti state by multistage sampling technique. The study adopted a non-randomised control group pretest post test design as described by Campbell and Stanley (1966); (1970). Four null hypotheses were tested at $P = 0.05$ level of significance. Hypotheses I, II and III were tested by using one way analysis of variance statistics. Findings showed that out of the three instructional strategies investigated, concept mapping was the best, because it stimulated students' interest in learning and also ensured meaningful learning of Basic science in schools. It was however recommended that the use of concept mapping for the effective teaching of Basic science in schools should be encouraged while the use of conventional instructional strategy should be discouraged henceforth because it promotes rote learning.

Keywords: *Effects, Concepts, Mapping, Scaffolding, Strategies, Learning, outcomes and Basic sciences.*

Introduction

Science is a body of organized knowledge and a process of inquiry that is generally concerned with finding out about things in our environment. Science has two major components, namely: Science process skills and science content.

The content of science is the knowledge we accumulate about our environment while the process skills deal with ways in which scientists go about gathering knowledge about the environment. Such ways or basic process skills include observation, measurement, inference, classification, prediction and communication etc. In using the stated process skills, the scientist has to be honest and open minded about the information obtained. It is important to note that all scientific knowledge are temporary and must be testable. In this context, scientific theories and laws are temporary, they can change when there is overwhelming evidences against such theories and laws. This is called paradigm shift. However, science has limitations because whatever cannot be observed is out of the realm of science. Hence, experience such as grief, happiness and emotions etc. cannot be explained by science.

Science is taught or included as a component of Basic science and Technology curriculum in junior secondary schools so as to help pupils to be able to explain events in nature and hence enable them (pupil) to be able to think and reason in a logical manner (Ilugbusi, 2007; FGN UBE, 2011).

This however, justifies why Basic science is made compulsory to be passed by any student at the junior secondary school level before he/she could proceed to the senior secondary school or for Technical Education. Despite the importance of Basic science to the Nigerian Government's new 9 year Basic Education programme in science and technology, students learning outcome in Basic Science at both Junior Secondary School I, Junior Secondary School II and Junior Secondary School III have continued to decline significantly and have now assumed a worrisome dimension. (Ekiti State Ministry of Education's reports on the outcome of 2011 JSS Examination).

Poor learning outcomes according to Arnadin, Mintzes, Dunn and Shafer (1984) is due to the fact that most students of science lack many of the

basic learning skills and study habits needed for success. At this juncture, we can then ask ourselves, how can we help Basic science students to learn meaningfully? Some studies have been carried out on new teaching and learning strategies which can eventually ensure meaningful learning (Arndudin, et al 1984; Arinkmann, 2003a, 2003b; Brown, 2005, 2007; Rachel Stuyf, 2002).

Some of these strategies are advance organizer, concept mapping, scaffolding and framing etc. Empirical researches on the above mentioned teaching and learning strategies hitherto appeared to produce inconclusive and conflicting reports on their effects on students learning outcomes in science. (Arnadin et al, 1984; Novak, 1990, 1996, Brinkmann, 2003a, 2003b and Ilugbusi, 2011) Consequently, this study examined and compared the effects of concept mapping and scaffolding as instructional strategies on students' learning outcomes in Basic science in Junior Secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Conceptual Framework

Concept maps were first introduced by Novak (1990) as a research tool and based on the learning theory of David Ausubel. Concept maps show in a special graphical way in form on a flowchart how concepts are related to a given topic together with their interrelationship.

The method of concept mapping was developed specifically to tap into a learner's cognitive structure and to externalize what the learner already knows (Novak and Govin, 1984). According to Ausubel's statement, "The most important single factor influencing learning is what the learner already knows, ascertain this and teach him accordingly" (Ausubel et al 1980). Although, the primer intention was to use concept mapping in research, it was found to be a useful tool in helping students to learn how to learn (Novak and Govin, 1984; Novak, 1990, 1996). Consequently, concept mapping has

been used also as educational tool, above all in science teaching. According to Brinkmann (2003), concept maps have been found to be useful in a variety of applications, in the teaching of different aspects of science and mathematics at all levels ranging from primary school to senior high school. Concept maps generally;

- (i) help to organize information on a topic
- (ii) facilitate meaningful learning by aiding in organizing and understanding new subject matter
- (iii) may serve as memory aid and
- (iv) a powerful tool for identifying students' knowledge structures, especially misconceptions or alternative conceptions.

According to Arndudin, et al (1984), the six steps of concept map making as adapted from Novak, (1990, 1996) are as follows:

- (i) Read a short section of a book or review a portion of your class notes.
- (ii) Identify the major concept by listening or underlining
- (iii) List the concept where possible from most inclusive (most general) to least inclusive (most specific).
- (iv) Write the most concept at the top of the map, link it to least inclusive concept, label all lines with linking words that explain how each pair of concept is related. The map should be read from top to bottom.
- (v) Try to branch out
- (vi) Make cross links between two concepts that are already on the map. Draw these links with arrows so that the reader will be able to read conveniently in the intended direction.

Arndudin, et al (1984) find in their study that students who voluntarily chose to map consistently performed significantly better than non-mappers.

On the other hand, scaffolding instruction as a teaching strategy originated according to Rachael Van Der Stuyf (2002) from Lev Vygotsky's socio-cultural theory and his concept of the Zone of Proximal Development

(ZPD). The zone of proximal development is the distance between what children can do by themselves and the next learning that they can be helped to achieve with competent assistance (Raymond, 2000). The scaffolding teaching strategy provides individualized support based on the learner's ZPD. In scaffolding instruction, a more knowledgeable person provides scaffolds or supports to facilitate the learners' development. The more capable person provides individualized support based on the learner's ZPD. In scaffolding instruction, a more knowledgeable person provides scaffolds or supports to facilitate the learners development. The more capable person provides the scaffolds so that the learner can accomplish (with assistance) the tasks that he or she could otherwise not complete, thus, helping the learner through the ZPD (Branford, Brown and Cocking, 2000).

Scaffolding instruction is the "rule of teachers and others in supporting the learner's development and providing support structures to get the next stage or level" (Raymond, 2000). An important aspect of scaffolding instruction is that the scaffolds are temporary, as the learner's abilities increase, the scaffolding provided by the more knowledgeable person is progressively withdrawn, and finally the learner is able to complete the task or master the concepts independently.

According to Mckenzie (2000) as quoted by Van Der Stuyf (2002). Scaffolding;

- (i) provides clear direction and reduces students' confusion
- (ii) Clarifies purpose
- (iii) Keeps students on task
- (iv) Clarifies expectations and incorporates assessment and feedback and
- (v) Reduces uncertainty, surprise and disappointment.

Purpose

This study examined and compared the effects of concept mapping and scaffolding as instructional strategies on students' learning outcomes in Basic Science in Junior secondary schools in Ekiti State of Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to find out, which of the two instructional strategies will better enhance students' learning outcomes in Basic Science in Ekiti State.

Research Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at $P = 0.05$ level of significance in this study.

- (1) There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and scaffolding instructional strategies in Ekiti State.
- (2) There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.
- (3) There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to scaffolding and conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.
- (4) There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping, scaffolding and the conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.

Method

The study adopted a non-randomised control group pretest-post test design as described by Campbell and Stanley (1966), (1970). The subject for the study were 300 JSS II Basic science students consisting of three groups randomly selected from five Junior secondary schools in Ekiti State of Nigeria by using multistage sampling technique. Each of the three groups consisted

of 120 (80 boys and 40 girls) students. The subjects' ages ranged from 11 years to 13 years with a mean age of 12 years. There were two experimental groups;

- (i) Those taught with concept mapping strategy (E_1)
- (ii) Those taught with scaffolding strategy (E_2) and
- (iii) One control group (c). The three groups received lesson on the following recurrent themes of Basic Science and Technology curriculum for 6 weeks, you and your environment, living and non-living things, you and technology and you and energy. The only difference was using scaffolding strategy while the control group was also taught the same content by using the conventional teaching method. All the three groups were taught by the same teacher for six weeks.

Instrumentation

Two different tests (i) Pretest and (ii) Post test on the content area specified above were constructed, validated and used for data collection by the researcher.

After construction, both the pretest and post test were given to three experts in science education as well as three experts in tests and measurement. Consequently, the face, content and construct validity of both test items were ascertained. Both the pretest and post test contained 50 items each. Both tests were later trial tested on 100 subjects which were not part of the original study sample and the reliability indices of both the pretest and post test were computed by Cronbach formula to be 0.74 and 0.75 respectively. These two indices are however considered good enough for this kind of study according to Alonge (2004) and Macintosh (1974).

09	88	09	31	120	E_2
07	70	08	38	120	Control
				360	Total

Method of Data Collection

Before the commencement of the actual teaching, pretest was administered on all the three groups. Thereafter, groups I, II and III received lesson for 6 weeks on the stated content area in Basic science by using concept mapping strategy, scaffolding strategy and conventional method respectively. After the sixth week, post test was administered on all the three groups and the scripts were marked and their scores were arranged, coded and subjected to the necessary statistical analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

Before descriptive and inferential statistics were used to test all the stated hypotheses at $P=0.05$ level of significance. Specifically, hypotheses I, II and III were tested by using one way analysis of variance (one way ANOVA). Turkey's HSD post hoc comparison test was also applied to the data in order to determine the comparative nature of the effect of each strategy. Eta squared comparison test was also used to determine the strengths of effects for the sources of between group variability.

Results and Discussion

Table I: Descriptive Statistics of Pre Test and Post Test scores of the three groups in Basic Science.

Group	N	Pre - Test		Post - Test	
		X_e	SD_e	X_o	SD_o
E_1	120	45	07	94	11
E_2	120	31	06	88	09
Control	120	38	08	70	07
Total	360				

The descriptive statistical analysis in table I above showed the students' learning outcomes in both their pretest and post test scores. The table showed the mean and SD of pretest scores of groups taught by using concept mapping, scaffolding and conventional strategies in Basic Science as also shown in table I above are, 94 and 11, 88 and 09, 70 and 07 respectively.

The results showed that the post-test mean scores of all groups were greater than their pre-test mean scores in Basic science. Hence the treatment conditions significantly enhanced students' learning outcomes in Basic science. Results in table I also showed that the group taught by using concept mapping instructional strategy (E_1) performed best out of the three groups with a post test mean score of 94 and a standard deviation of 11. These results corroborated previous research findings by Novak (1990), (1996), Brinkmann (2003)a, (2003)b, Hasemann and Mansfield (1995), Malone and Dekkers (1984), Novak and Carfias (2006) and Arnaudin et al (1984). Resultantly, concept mapping is the best instructional strategy for teaching Basic science in Junior secondary schools in Ekiti State because it ensures meaningful learning and facilitates learning than other strategies investigated.

Hypothesis I: There is no significant difference in the learning and outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and scaffolding instructional strategies in Ekiti State.

Table II: Independent t test analysis on the learning outcome of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and scaffolding strategies in Ekiti State.

Variables	N	X	SD	tc	tt	df	Result
Concept mapping Group	120	94	11				
Scaffolding Group	120	88	09	4.62	1.96	238	*
Total	240						

P = 0.05

*: Significant result

The t-test analysis in table II above showed that the $t_c = 4.62$ is greater than the $t_t = 1.96$ at $P = 0.05$ level of significance and $df = 238$. The $t_c = 4.62$ is significant statistically and hence null hypothesis I is rejected. Consequently, there was a significant difference between the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and scaffolding instructional strategies in Ekiti State. The mean and standard deviation of 94 and 11 obtained by students taught by using concept mapping strategy as compared to the mean and standard deviation of 88 and 09 obtained by students taught using scaffolding showed a generally better over all learning outcomes by students exposed to concept mapping strategy in Basic Science in Ekiti State junior secondary schools. These findings are in line with previous research findings by Novak and Carfias (2006), Novak (1990), (1996), Brinkmann (2003)a, (2003)b and Arnandin et al (1984) who found in their respective studies that concept mapping is a very effective instructional

strategy because it ensures meaningful learning. They also found out that students who voluntarily choose to map consistently perform better than non-mappers in science and mathematics.

Hypothesis II: There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.

Table III: t test analysis on the learning outcome of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.

Variables	N	X	SD	tc	tt	df	Result
Concept mapping Group	120	94	11				
Scaffolding Group	120	70	07	20.16	1.96	238	*
Total	240						

P = 0.05

*: Significant result

The independent t-test analysis in table III showed that the $t_c = 20.16$ is greater than the $t_t = 1.96$ at $P = 0.05$ level of significance and $df = 238$. The $t_c = 20.16$ is significant and thus, the null hypothesis II is rejected.

Hence, there was a significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping and conventional instructional strategies in junior secondary schools in Ekiti State.

A cursory look at the means and standard deviations of both groups in the table showed a generally better learning outcome by Basic science students exposed to concept mapping instructional strategy in secondary

schools in Ekiti State. These findings agreed in-to-to with previous similar research findings by Hasemann and Mansfield (1995) and Arnoudin et al (1984) who found that science and mathematics students who voluntarily choose to map consistently outperform non-mappers.

Hypothesis III: There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to scaffolding and conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.

Table IV: t test analysis on the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to scaffolding and conventional strategies in Ekiti State.

Variables	N	X	SD	tc	tt	df	Result
Concept mapping Group	120	88	09				
Scaffolding Group	120	70	07	17.29	1.96	238	*
Total	240						

P = 0.05

*: Significant result

The t-test analysis in table IV above showed that the $t_c = 17.29$ is greater than the $t_t = 1.96$ at $P = 0.05$ level of significance and $df = 238$. The $t_c = 17.29$ is significant and hence null hypothesis III is rejected. Therefore, there was a significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to scaffolding and conventional strategy in Basic science in junior secondary schools in Ekiti State.

These findings are in line with similar previous research findings by Rachel Van Der Stuyf (2002), Raymond (2000) and Mckenzie (2000) who found in their studies that Scaffolding facilitates learning and also ensures

meaningful learning in science and mathematics.

Hypothesis IV: There is no significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping, scaffolding and the conventional instructional strategies in Ekiti State.

Table V: One way Analysis of variance (one way ANOVA) summary table on the learning outcome of Basic science students exposed to the three instructional strategies under investigation in Ekiti State.

Source of Variances	N	Sun of Squares	Mean Square	Fc	Ft	Result
Between Groups	2	192	90	8.18	2.00	
Within Groups	357	247	11			*
Total	359	439	101			

$P = 0.05$

*: Significant result

The one way ANOVA analysis in table V above showed that the $F_c = 8.18$ is greater than $F_t = 2.00$ at $P=0.05$ level of significance and df of 2 and 357 for the numerator and denominator respectively.

The $F_c = 8.18$ is significant and hence null hypothesis IV is rejected. Consequently, there was a significant difference in the learning outcomes of Basic science students exposed to concept mapping, scaffolding and the conventional instructional strategies in junior secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Conclusions and Recommendations

Findings of this study revealed that out of all the instructional strategies investigated, concept mapping was the most effective because it stimulated students' interest in learning and also ensured meaningful learning of Basic science at the Junior secondary schools in Ekiti State.

Scaffolding instructional strategy was also found to be better than the conventional instructional strategy because it de-emphasizes rote learning in Basic science and also assisted the weaker or less intelligent students to learn how to learn meaningfully in Basic science classes from better students known as scaffolds.

The conventional instructional strategy which is still in vogue in most junior secondary schools in Ekiti State was found to be totally obsolete, because the strategy could not cope with the challenges of the new 9 years Basic science and Technology curriculum which was introduced to lower, middle and upper Basic classes (i.e. Primary and Junior secondary schools) recently by the Federal Government of Nigeria.

Finding also revealed that most of the teachers in the Junior secondary schools knew little or nothing about concept mapping and scaffolding instructional strategies. Those of them who knew little about the strategies did not know how to use them effectively to achieve meaningful learning in basic science classes. It was also discovered that the very few of the practicing teachers who attempted to use concept mapping and scaffolding instructional strategies could neither cope with nor surmount the challenges associated with the utilization of the two strategies in Basic science classrooms.

Based on the findings of this study and the conclusion above, the following recommendations are made:

1. The use of concept mapping for effective teaching of Basic Science in junior secondary schools should be encouraged because it ensures

meaningful learning.

2. Students in Basic science classes in the Junior secondary schools should be divided into three groups, that is; high ability, medium ability and low ability levels so that those at the high ability level group would always serve as scaffolds to those in the medium and low ability levels in the class, so as to assist them to learn how to learn and hence ensures meaningful learning.
3. The use of conventional instructional strategy should be discouraged and stopped immediately because it encourages rote learning and it is obsolete.
4. UBEC, SUBEB, Governments and other stakeholders in education should organize regular seminars, workshops, and even conferences for practicing teachers of Basic science in the junior secondary schools so as to acquaint them with the necessary improved pedagogical skills needed to cope with the challenges associated with concept mapping and scaffolding.
5. In-service training should also be organized for practicing teachers of Basic science in junior secondary schools on the meaning, purposes, uses, applications and challenges of concept mapping and scaffoldings as teaching or instructional strategies as well as their remedies.

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